

Methodological Fundamentals of Teaching Bio Pharmacy in Higher Medical Education Institutions

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Abstract: This article will talk about the need for training, methodological basis in pre-existing medical higher education institutions. Why training methods are needed in the occupation of the shahs, in developed countries it is about the work being carried out on the Soha, and about the resistance to shaming in future doctors.

Keywords: student, medical higher education institution, bio pharmacy, developed countries, modern information technology, media competence, knowledge, qualifications, skills.

Introduction. In our country, complex scientific research is being carried out on modernizing national medical and pharmaceutical education, introducing international educational standards in this field, and current problems of public health protection. Action strategy on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 and the concept of development of the healthcare system of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2025: "Further improvement of the system of medical and pharmaceutical education and science, ensuring its integration into practical health care, methodical training of future doctors, the technology of organizing this process, methodical support, improving the system and mechanisms of competences related to activity and increasing the level of medical care" marked.

Large-scale reforms in the field of education carried out in the years of independence provided medical higher education institutions with modern educational laboratory equipment, updated educational programs, educational methodical literature in accordance with international requirements, and the educational process serves to increase the effectiveness of the introduction of advanced pedagogical and information communication technologies. In the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 in order to eliminate the emerging problems in the practical work: development of professional competencies of students due to the effective use of technologies..." was defined as a pedagogical necessity. Development of media literacy skills of students through the wide use of electronic textbooks, virtual educational technologies, multimedia electronic complexes in the educational process, as well as providing innovative education to students in the fields of activity, continuous improvement of professional skills and competences, education from media contents Scientific studies are being carried out on the training of modern specialists with media competence using the lim process. [1]

Research Methodology. According to the above information, the concept of "biopharmacy" was not founded by the American scientists Levi and Wagner, but by our compatriot Ibn Sina. However, it is inappropriate to consider them as the founders of biopharmacy just because the above-mentioned scientists used the term "biopharmacy"[2]. When the drug

enters the body, it undergoes complex processes, and then it shows its effect. The following is a simplified representation of the steps in this process:

Type of medicine. In the biofluid at the place of absorption of the drug, in the blood or tissues, the drug substance (or its fragmented parts) Excretion of drugs through the gastrointestinal tract, kidneys, lungs, and skin glands.

The first stage includes processes leading to the release of the bioactive substance from the type of drug taken and its absorption to the desired organ.

In the second stage, the drug that has passed into the biosuction is absorbed according to the laws of diffusion. Diffusion kinetics are influenced by pharmaceutical and physiological factors. Including alcohol activity, technological process, dissolution of drug type in liquid, decomposition, etc. Diffusion kinetics includes the properties and condition of the tissue membrane, tissue enzyme activity. Drug absorption depends on the patient's age, gender, body condition.

In the third stage, physiological factors take the main place, that is, drugs or their metabolites are distributed in the body (blood, tissue).

In the fourth stage, the main biochemical factors in the movement of drugs in the body are observed. In this case, the action and release of drugs or their metabolites in the biologic system takes place. Pharmaceutical factors greatly affect the rate of absorption of drugs into the body. These factors include chemical and physical states of drugs, excipients, drug type and route of administration, and effects of pharmaceutical processes.

The study of the above-mentioned factors in the form of introduction of drugs into the body, its action and effect is considered the basis of biopharmaceutics. So, Ibn Sina is the founder of the science of biopharmaceutics, and his famous work "Laws of Medicine" is considered the methodological basis of the science. Biopharmaceutics is mainly closely connected with the beginning of pharmacognosy and the technology of preparation of drugs with the period of emergence of human culture. Ibn Sina had a great influence on the development of medicine and pharmacy in the world today. 10 centuries ago, when Ibn Sina lived and worked, there was no independent pharmaceutical service, it had just separated from medicine and began to form independently[3]. Later, the composition of recipes and the complexity of their preparation technology, as well as the creation of new types of complex drugs, became difficult for judges (or doctors) to do alone. pharmacist) specialty appeared.

Discussion. In the context of modern medical education, the development of comprehensive and effective training methodologies is essential to prepare future healthcare professionals for the challenges they will face. This article has emphasized the importance of integrating contemporary teaching methods within medical higher education institutions, particularly in the field of biopharmacy. This integration not only facilitates the acquisition of knowledge but also fosters the development of critical skills and competencies required in the modern medical field. The need for innovative training methods is especially evident in the occupation of pharmacists and other healthcare professionals, where the rapid evolution of medical science and technology necessitates continuous learning and adaptation. In many developed countries, significant progress has been made in incorporating advanced pedagogical approaches, such as simulation-based learning, into medical curricula[4].

This approach allows students to gain practical experience in a controlled environment, bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world application. Resistance to new teaching methodologies can sometimes be observed, particularly among educators and institutions accustomed to traditional approaches. However, overcoming this resistance is crucial for the advancement of medical education. By adopting a more flexible and open-minded stance towards innovative teaching methods, medical higher education institutions

can better equip their students to handle the complexities of modern healthcare. The inclusion of simulation technologies and media literacy training, as highlighted in the concept of the development of the higher education system in Uzbekistan, serves as a vital step towards this goal.

Moreover, the discussion surrounding the origins and evolution of biopharmacy underscores the importance of understanding both the historical and scientific foundations of the field. The contributions of Ibn Sina, often regarded as a pioneer in the development of biopharmaceutics, provide a rich historical context that highlights the longstanding relationship between medicine and pharmacy. By appreciating the historical roots and methodological foundations of biopharmacy, educators can instill a deeper understanding and respect for the discipline in their students.

The study of biopharmaceutics, as outlined in this article, involves a complex interplay of pharmaceutical, physiological, and biochemical factors that influence drug absorption and efficacy. This understanding is critical not only for pharmacists but also for other healthcare professionals who must ensure the safe and effective use of medications. By focusing on the methodological aspects of biopharmacy, educators can better prepare students to contribute to the ongoing development of pharmaceutical science.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the integration of innovative training methodologies and the appreciation of historical and scientific foundations are essential for the advancement of medical education. By embracing these elements, medical higher education institutions can enhance the quality of education they provide, ensuring that future healthcare professionals are well-prepared to meet the demands of their profession. The ongoing efforts to modernize medical education in Uzbekistan, as discussed in this article, reflect a commitment to these principles, paving the way for a new generation of competent and skilled medical practitioners.

Any researcher, while conducting scientific research on a specific topic, first of all, relies on a certain methodology and uses scientific research methods that are available to realize his goal. A person always moves towards a certain goal. The result of his action is inextricably linked with the methods used in this activity, in addition to the nature of the moving subject and the object of the movement. This shows that the cognitive process must rely on a certain methodology and method. Methods and methodology are very important in the study of biopharmaceutics. F. Bacon compares the method to a torch that illuminates the path in the dark. Emphasizes that a certain problem cannot be positively solved by a false (false) way. Therefore, any researcher should have a research method that is a tool of knowledge and provides man with control over nature. F. Bacon chooses induction as such a method. This method requires science to rely on empirical analysis, observation and experimentation, and on this basis to understand causality and laws.

References:

1. Worsnop, C.M. (2004). *Media Literacy Through Critical Thinking*. NW Center for Excellence in Media Literacy, 60p.
2. Malakhovsky V. *Familiar and unfamiliar numbers*. – Kaliningrad: FGUIPP, 2004.
3. Buharkina M., Mosiyeva V. *New pedagogical and information technologies in the educational system*. - M., 2000. 3.
4. Solovev Yu. I. *Evolutsiya osnovnykh teoreticheskikh problem khimii*.— M.: Nauka, 1971, 380 p.
5. Social government portal: www.Ziyonet.uz.

6. Bermus A.G. Problemy i perspektivy realizatsii kompetentnostnogo pokhoda v obrazovanii. www.eidoc.ru. 2005, 09, <http://www.school.edu.ru> Universal education portal (in Russian)
7. Кобулова М. А. РОЛЬ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ //Journal of Integrated Education and Research. - 2022. - Т. 1. - . 5. - С. 12-16.